

The Wavefunction and its Relationship to a Dynamic Periodic Function

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Traditional quantum mechanics seems to start with the Schrodinger equation which is solved for a function called the wavefunction. This function multiplied by its complex conjugate is $P(x)$ (P =probability) or spatial density which is a measurable. There have often been questions as to why quantum mechanics is based on this square root of probability or spatial density. In this note, we argue a quantum particle is modeled by $\exp(ipx)$, for example a free electron. This is also part of traditional quantum mechanics, but $\exp(ipx)$ is called the wavefunction of the electron. We argue $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamical, periodic function which models a special kind of motion (a kind of zitterbewegung). This is not the same motion as a classical particle translating from one point to another. The electron moves from one point to another in a manner which involves two dimensions i.e. $\cos(kx) + i \sin(kx)$.

Next, we consider the electron (or another quantum particle) in a potential $V(x)$. We use conditional probability $f_p \exp(ipx) / [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)]$ ((1)) as $P(p/x)$. The denominator is the wavefunction $W(x)$ and one can calculate an average $p^2/2m$ and obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The point we wish to make, is that there seem to be special translational properties in terms of x and p of $W(x)$ and f_p , similar to those of $\exp(ipx)$. At first glance, $W(x)$ is simply a normalization constant which happens to become part of the Schrodinger equation. Thus, we argue that one begins with $\exp(ipx)$ and obtains a resonance which tries to mimic the p and x translational properties of $\exp(ipx)$. It turns out that $W(x)$ and f_p have exactly these properties, but on a conditional average level. We try to argue this why quantum mechanics is so focused on these two functions.

Translational Properties of $\exp(ipx)$

It seems quantum mechanics is heavily based on $\exp(ipx)$ which is a dynamic, periodic math function. If one considers $\exp(ip(x+b))$, where b is tiny, the change in $\exp(ipx)$ is $ip \exp(ipx)$, thus translation is related to the momentum. In classical physics, translation occurs because of momentum, but one does not have a zitterbewegung type motion with shifts between the real $\cos(px)$ and the imaginary $\sin(px)$. Furthermore, in classical physics, spatial density is proportional to $1/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. If a classical particle moves at a constant speed, there is no change in the square root of $1/v(x)$ from one x point to another, but there is a change in $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the motion of the quantum particle is different even though $\exp(ipx)$ has momentum p and energy $p^2/2m$.

If a quantum particle, modeled by $\exp(ipx)$, is added to a region with a potential $V(x)$, one may postulate it will scatter into different states $\exp(ik_1 x)$, $\exp(ik_2 x)$ with weights $f(k_i)$. Thus, the average momentum, if the particle is at x may be written as:

$$\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = \sum_p p P(p/x) = \frac{[\sum_p p f_p \exp(ipx)]}{[\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)]} \quad ((2))$$

One may also calculate $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$ as this is related to the variance of $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$:

$$\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle = \frac{[\sum_p p^2 f_p \exp(ipx)]}{[\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)]} \quad ((2))$$

In these definitions, $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$. This is traditionally called the wavefunction, but is only a normalization function here. The interesting point, however, is that $W(x)$ translates in a similar way to $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.:

$$\exp[ip(x+b)] = \exp(ipx) + ipb \exp(ipx)$$

$$\begin{aligned} W(x+b) &= W(x) + b \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \text{ to first order} = W(x) + b [\sum_p ip f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) \\ &= W(x) + bi \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((3)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $W(x)$ is a function which mimics the space translational behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$, but with p replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$.

A free electron is described by $\exp(ipx)$. This describes its two dimensional "zitterbewegung" type cycle as it moves from one point to another. Thus, if one tries to take an average of this particle in a region with a potential, one is already expecting this kind of $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ motion, even in an average sense. This may help explain why interference is used. In other words, it seems that for $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ one is taking an average at point x assuming a quantum resonance is a kind of "averaged" $\exp(ipx)$ (made up of many $\exp(ikx)$ with weights f_k). (For a bound state, $W(x)$ is real, but as one takes the average over p , the real part receives positive and negative values from $\cos(kx)$ for the different k values. This seems like "interference", but there is only particle at x at any time. This particle, however, can have a range of values ($\cos(kx)$ values from -1 to 1) at x , so the average is based on these values with the assumption that $i \sin(kx)$ also has a range of values. Thus, the wavefunction, even with a potential $V(x)$, may be periodic.)

The link seems to hold also for $\exp(ipx)$ and f_p , with respect to changes in p . Thus, f_p also has special properties. Consider $d/dp f_p$. This is proportional to the change in the weight f_p as p is changed.

$$\exp[i(p+q)x] = \exp(ipx) + ixq \exp(ipx) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{Here } q \text{ is a tiny change in momentum.}$$

This indicates there is a change in $\exp(ipx)$ between two momenta p and $p+q$. Interestingly, f_p , the scattering weight has a similar relationship, but based on an average x .

$$f_p = \int dx W(x) \exp(-ipx) \text{ so:}$$

$$f(p+q) = f(p) + q \frac{d}{dp} f(p) = f(p) + q (-i) \int dx W(x) (-x) \exp(ipx) = f(p) - iq \langle x \text{ conditional} \rangle$$

Thus, the scattering resonance $W(x)$ which forms when one places a quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$ into a region with a potential $V(x)$ maintains, in a conditional average sense, the x and p translational behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$. In general, $W(x)$ is a normalization constant and $f(p)$ a weight for $P(p/x)$. For $P(x/p)$ their roles are reversed. This may help to explain why $W(x)$, the wavefunction, and $f(p)$, play a pivotal role in quantum mechanics.

Out of curiosity, consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation written with $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ both expressed as Fourier series. Then:

$$\sum_k V_k f(p-k) = (E - p^2/2m) f(p) \quad ((4b))$$

Taking the derivative of ((4b)) with respect to p gives:

$$\sum_k V_k \frac{d}{dp} f(p-k) = (E - p^2/2m) \frac{d}{dp} f(p) - p/m f(p) \quad ((4c))$$

If one considers $f(p)$ for the oscillator ground state, i.e. $\exp(-b p^2)$ where $\sqrt{km}/2 = b$ then:

$$\sum_k V_k (p-k) \exp(-b (p-k)^2) = (E_0 - p^2/2m + 1/m2b) p \exp(-bp^2) \quad ((4d))$$

Here E_0 is the oscillator ground state energy. Thus, $p \exp(-bp^2)$ seems to be a solution of ((4b)), the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Here p is the first Hermite polynomial, but $p \exp(-bp^2)$ is also $d/dp f(p)$ (gs oscillator). $p \exp(-bp^2)$ is also the first order change between $f(p)$ and $f(p+q)$ where q is tiny.

Link to Classical Kinetic Energy

Even though $\exp(ipx)$ does not behave in the same manner as a classical particle, $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is directly related to $.5mv(x)v(x)$ which is the classical kinetic energy by:

$$1/2m \langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle = .5mv(x)v(x)$$

One may inquire into the relevance of $1/2m \langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$ $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$. This is a kinetic energy type term which does not equal $.5mv(x)v(x)$. The two seem to be related, however, if one multiplies each by $P(x)$ and integrates. Thus, they represent, the same integrated full average (not conditional average) kinetic energy in the system. $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$, however, is linked to the actual classical kinetic energy at point x which is related to the potential $V(x)$. Again, there is interference in the calculation of $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$. For a free electron one has: $p^2/2m [\cos(px) + i \sin(px)]$. For the electron in the potential, one averages: $p^2/2m \cos(px) + i p^2/2m \sin(px)$

with f_p weights for each f_p and a normalization . It is as if the kinetic energy is becoming part of the zitterbewegung motion according to this type of “interference” averaging.

Entropy Considerations

In the discussion above, conditional probabilities were used, i.e. $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$. It may be shown (1) that $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ for $W(x)$ real and $P(p)=f_p f_p$ for f_p real. (Otherwise one uses W^*W and $f_p^* f_p$.) One may consider spatial and momentum translations for $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ as well.

$$d/dx P(x) = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x) = 2 P(x) \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((5)) \text{ and}$$

$$d/dp P(p) = 2 f_p d/dp f_p = 2 P(p) \langle x \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((6))$$

Interestingly, these both may be recast in terms of spatial and momentum Shannon’s entropy density changes. From ((5)), we have:

$$-d/dx s(x) = -2 s(x) \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle + 2 P(x) \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((7))$$

And

$$-d/dp s(p) = -2 s(p) \langle x \text{ conditional} \rangle + 2 P(p) \langle x \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((8))$$

where :

$$s(x) = -P(x) \ln[P(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad s(p) = -P(p) \ln[P(p)].$$

Conclusion

$W(x)$ and f_p , mimic $\exp(ipx)$ in terms of translational changes in x and p , but with conditional average x and p values, where $P(p/x)=f_p \exp(ipx)/ W(x)$ is used to calculate the average. We argue this may help explain why $W(x)$ and f_p are important in quantum mechanics. It seems $\exp(ipx)$ is the model of a dynamical free quantum particle, and when it interacts with a potential $V(x)$, it is the math functions $W(x)$ and f_p which have similar translational properties as $\exp(ipx)$, except that they use conditional average x and p values. One may ask why one should be interested in such translational properties in the first place, but it seems they are important to the dynamic and periodic behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$. For example, translation in x shows how $\exp(ipx)$ moves and is linked to p (momentum). A quantum particle does not move like a classical one which simply translates from point to point. This in turn, affects, translational changes in $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ which can be recast into changes in Shannon’s x and p entropies.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Density as Wavefunction Squared (preprint, zenodo, 2018)

